

(formerly the European Circular Bioeconomy Policy Initiative)

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EBB BRIEFING PAPER ON THE PACKAGING AND PACKAGING WASTE REGULATION

The European Council on 16 December 2024 formally adopted the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation, in what's described as the final legislative step to a two years-long process.

It's expected to be signed on Dec. 19, and publication in the Official Journal of the European Union usually occurs around 20 days after signature. The regulation will be applied 18 months after officially published. As a Regulation the law automatically enters into force in all the EU and requires no transcription into national laws.

The regulation contains topline targets to reduce packaging waste from a 2018 baseline by 5% by 2030, 10% by 2035 and 15% by 2040.

Other tenets of the regulation, which aims to address the full lifecycle of packaging, include:

- Restrictions on single-use plastic packaging for certain food, beverages and condiments consumed on-site; pre-packed produce; small personal care products at hotels; and "very lightweight" plastic bags
- 2030 and 2040 targets for minimum recycled content, lightweighting packaging and minimizing substances of concern like PFAS, including requiring 65% postconsumer plastic in most plastic packaging come 2040
- Binding reuse targets for 2030 (with different thresholds for different types of packaging) and a requirement that takeout establishments allow customers to bring their own containers for filling at no additional charge

There are several deadlines within the legal text for the Commission to adopt secondary legislation. Therefore, the focus now shifts to the timely development of secondary legislation and the implementation of follow-up actions required under the Regulation. These steps are crucial to addressing the PPWR's broad scope and complexity while providing the industry with the necessary framework to prepare for compliance.

The PPWR emphasizes the importance of packaging that is reusable, recyclable, or compostable by 2030. It places significant emphasis on sustainable packaging solutions, with

biobased plastics emerging as a key enabler of the EU's circular economy and climate neutrality goals.

Biobased plastics, derived from renewable resources, such as biomass, will play a pivotal role in reducing reliance on fossil-based materials while cutting greenhouse gas emissions over their lifecycle by utilizing carbon absorbed during plant growth.

The use of certified biobased feedstocks in packaging not only ensures reduced carbon emissions but also drives industrial decarbonization and provides an alternative to single-use plastics. Additionally, biobased plastics can support the packaging sector's targets for recyclability, helping manufacturers meet regulatory requirements.

Their integration into packaging solutions aligns with the EU's overarching ambitions to increase packaging circularity and minimize environmental impact while maintaining the performance and functionality required for packaging applications.

Compostable packaging solutions certified to European standards (e.g., EN 13432), also offer unique benefits for specific applications such as food packaging, where they enhance organic waste management and reduce contamination in recycling streams.

The PPWR values compostability as a product requirement and not an end-of-life guidance. Yet even though a limited number of compostable applications are made mandatory, the regulation risks confusion among manufacturers, economic operators and citizens, undermining the level playing field ensured by the EU Internal Market. Indeed, it will be up to Member States to decide whether, in addition to the mandatory ones, other applications should be compostable, provided they comply with the obligation to set up separate collection of bio-waste in their territory and ensure composting infrastructure is in place.

The provisional text adopted in April 2024 by the European Parliament can be found here [Texts adopted - Packaging and packaging waste - Wednesday, 24 April 2024](#) but the final text to be published in the Official Journal may differ due to translation issues as well as final amendments approved in the Trialogue Sessions. Therefore please refer to the final text when published in January 2025.

Producers and consumers of biodegradable (certified compostable) and/or biobased materials to be used for packaging should study the text attentively because the Regulation creates market opportunities where biowaste is collected and compostable packaging can be co-collected for industrial composting and/or anaerobic digestion; in other jurisdictions, where biowaste treatment is undeveloped, compostable packaging will have limited applications.

As the separate collection of biowaste is now an obligation across the EU since January 1st 2024, it is foreseeable that the possible access of compostable packaging to co-collection with biowaste will increase. However, this transition is likely to be long and slow as resistance to implementing biowaste collections is still very high.

The recent report of Biobased Industries Consortium and Zero Waste Europe shows that still in 2023 that some 74% of biowaste is incinerated or landfilled. [Bio-waste generation in the EU: Current capture levels and future potential – Second edition - Zero Waste Europe](#)